

A Kinetic Study of Solvent Effect on Alkali catalysed Hydrolysis of Ethyl 3-Hydroxybenzoate in Aquo-DMSO and Aquo-propan-2-ol Media

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Kinetics of alkali catalysed hydrolysis of ethyl 3-hydroxybenzoate have been studied in aquo-DMSO and aquo-propan-2-ol media at varying compositions at different temperatures. Rate of reaction was found to decrease with increasing concentration of both the solvents. The activation parameters have been evaluated and the variation in these properties has been explained on the basis of solvation changes of the transition state. Further, the rate of hydrolysis of the ester was also compared with ethyl 2-hydroxybenzoate and the difference in the rates of these esters has been explained in the light of difference in their molecular structure.

The effect of solvent on the alkali catalysed hydrolysis of esters have received continued attention, but the explanations put forward are not satisfactory. Considering ester hydrolysis as ion-dipole type of reactions and assuming the predominance of electrostatic effects various contradictory views¹⁻¹⁰ on kinetic investigations on rate changes are reported in literature. Some of these have supported the views predicted by Parker² as well as Roberts³ about the rate enhancement by dipolar aprotic solvents like DMSO etc. However, some workers observed decrease in hydrolysis rate by various aprotic as well as protic solvents. A considerable amount of work has been carried out on the solvent effect of simple aliphatic and aromatic esters, but so far as the phenolic esters are concerned, only a few reports have been published and that with *ortho*-phenolic esters. A review of the literature reveals that no attempt has been made on *meta*-phenolic esters, which are likely to give interesting result due to the change in position of substituent. Therefore, it was thought worthwhile to study the effect of the solvents DMSO and propan-2-ol on the alkali catalysed hydrolysis of ethyl 3-hydroxybenzoate.

Results and Discussion

Tables 1 and 2 reveal that rate constant decreases with increasing percentage of both the organic solvents at all temperatures in accordance with the qualitative prediction of Hughes and Ingold⁴ as well as of Hocksmith and Amis⁵. DMSO

and propan-2-ol both being poor anion solvator, their increase in aqueous medium will facilitate the

TABLE 1—SPECIFIC RATE CONSTANT VALUES ($k \times 10^2 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ min}^{-1}$) ALKALI CATALYSED HYDROLYSIS OF ETHYL 3-HYDROXYBENZOATE IN AQUO-DMSO MEDIUM

Temp. °C	DMSO % (v/v)				
	10	20	40	50	70
20	8.3	5.7	4.1	2.9	2.1
25	10.1	7.7	5.6	4.2	2.8
30	13.0	9.9	7.7	5.2	4.2
35	16.8	13.4	10.1	8.2	5.6
45	26.1	23.8	18.7	17.6	12.7

TABLE 2—SPECIFIC RATE CONSTANT VALUES ($k \times 10^2 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ min}^{-1}$) ALKALI CATALYSED HYDROLYSIS OF ETHYL 3-HYDROXYBENZOATE IN AQUO-PROPAN-2-OL MEDIUM

Temp. °C	Propan-2-ol % (v/v)			
	10	20	30	40
25	6.9	5.4	4.6	4.2
30	9.8	7.5	5.8	5.1
35	14.2	9.3	7.4	6.5
40	18.4	12.5	9.4	7.9
45	24.0	16.2	12.0	9.7

desolvation of ions already solvated by water molecule. Since initial and transition states (both being anions differing in size and charge) cannot be equally desolvated, the rate will be affected by such

specific solvation changes. Thus it appears that transition state is more desolvated than the initial state in case of DMSO as the rate decreases with increase in DMSO content in the medium and this is the main cause of increase of E_c values (Table 3).

TABLE 3—VALUES OF E_c , ΔH^* , ΔS^* AND ΔG^* IN AQUA-DMSO MEDIUM

% DMSO (v/v)	E_c kJ mol ⁻¹	ΔH^* kJ mol ⁻¹	ΔS^* at 30° JK mol ⁻¹	ΔG^* at 30° kJ mol ⁻¹
10	36.20	32.05	-189.98	89.61
20	43.72	41.81	-160.05	90.31
50	53.37	51.98	-129.79	91.30
70	60.02	57.65	-115.00	92.50

Further a strange behaviour is also observed by plotting $\log k$ against mole % of organic solvent (Figs. 1 and 2). The plots show that the rate decreases more sharply in water-enriched medium, but

Fig. 1. Plots of $\log k$ vs mol % of DMSO at different temperatures.

at about 25 mole % of DMSO it assumes an asymptotic form, which may be due to formation of the complex of the composition DMSO.....2 H₂O at this mole %. Similar observations were obtained by previous workers^{11,12}. Further, it is obvious from Fig. 2 that in propan-2-ol enriched medium, i.e. after 40% of solvent composition no reproducible results were obtained, which may be due to abrupt change taking place in the structure of the solvent.

Activation parameters : E_c (iso-composition activation energy), ΔH^* , ΔS^* and ΔG^* values were evaluated by usual methods for both the solvent media (Tables 3 and 4). The E_c or ΔH^* values increase in aquo-DMSO and decrease in aquo-propan-

2-ol with increasing proportion of organic solvent in the media. The increase in E_c values with the increase of DMSO content in the reaction mixture

Fig. 2. Plots of $\log k$ vs mol % of propan-2-ol at different temperatures.

indicates progressive destabilisation of transition state on being transferred from the aqueous to aquo-DMSO system and thus resulting decrease in rate. The increase in ΔS^* (Table 3) suggests the formation of a more mobile transition state, which also supports the contention of desolvation of transition state in case of aquo-DMSO media. The decrease in E_c values with increase of propan-2-ol content in the reaction mixture indicates that either the initial state is more desolvated as compared to the transition state or the initial state is more desolvated and which transition state is solvated, but the decrease in ΔS^* values (Table 4) favours the latter. Further, decrease in ΔS^* values also suggests that transition

TABLE 4—VALUES OF E_c , ΔH^* , ΔS^* AND ΔG^* IN PROPAN-2-OL MEDIUM

% Propan-2-ol (v/v)	E_c kJ mol ⁻¹	ΔH^* kJ mol ⁻¹	ΔS^* at 30° JK ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹	ΔG^* at 30° kJ mol ⁻¹
10	50.74	51.58	-127.86	90.32
20	42.88	40.25	-167.26	91.03
30	36.78	35.20	-186.25	91.63
40	33.44	31.06	-201.14	92.00

state is relatively stabilised more and more with the addition of propan-2-ol which seems to be main reason to cause decrease in the rate in spite of de-

crease in E_c values in aquo-propan-2-ol medium. The variation of ΔH^* , ΔS^* and ΔG^* with mole % are found to be non-linear in both the aquo-organic solvent media. The non-linearity in these properties is indicative of selective solvation taking place in the medium as reported by other workers^{7,13,14}. The plot of ΔH^* and ΔS^* is found to be a straight line showing the obedience of Barclay and Butler rule¹⁵ in both the solvent mixtures. Further, the value of isokinetic temperature is found to be well within the range of 300–400 as suggested by Leffler and Grunwald¹⁶ in case of existence of weak, but positive solute-solvent interaction in both the solvent systems.

Comparison of rate of hydrolysis of ethyl 3-hydroxy benzoate with ethyl 2-hydroxybenzoate : On perusal of Tables 1 and 5 it is apparent that the extent of decrease is greater in ethyl 3-hydroxybenzoate than ethyl 2-hydroxybenzoate. The greater

TABLE 5—SPECIFIC RATE CONSTANT VALUES ($k \times 10^2 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ min}^{-1}$) ALKALI CATALYSED HYDROLYSIS OF ETHYL 2-HYDROXYBENZOATE IN AQUO-DMSO MEDIUM

Temp. °C	DMSO % (v/v)				
	10	20	40	50	70
20	18.0	14.4	9.4	7.2	3.3
25	32.6	24.7	17.3	14.1	6.8
30	55.0	45.2	35.5	26.6	13.5
35	104.3	82.0	57.8	49.8	26.0

decrease can be attributed to low electrostatic repulsion and no possibility of hydrogen bond formation between hydrogen atom of hydroxyl group and oxygen atom of carboxylate ion due to larger distance between hydroxyl group and carboxylate ion in comparison to the latter.

Experimental

All the chemicals except the ester (Aldrich) were of AnalaR grades. DMSO and propan-2-ol were purified by standard methods. Water used was double-distilled from alkaline KMnO_4 . A water thermostat (UNICO 0336) was used for carrying out

the experiments. The reaction mixtures were prepared using varying amounts of purified solvent (DMSO/propan-2-ol), water and calculated volume of 0.5 N NaOH. The reaction mixture was thermostated for 0.5 h and weighed amount of the ester was added to it. Aliquots (5 ml) of the reaction mixture, removed at different intervals of time, were estimated titrimetrically using standard baryta solution. The rate constant was computed by graphical method and values were reproducible within $\pm 2\%$.

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